

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MABJAIA****FIRST NAME: AUGUSTO****PROGRAM CODE: DEPI****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 4%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

ACADEMIC WRITING EXAM

1. Plagiarism is an anti-ethic practice carrying academic penalties. What is the most complete definition of plagiarism?

- An act of using or presenting words, ideas, statistics, and other relevant information through quotations, paraphrasing, or summarizing without giving credit to the original author or source by due citation and referencing.¹**
- Unaware use of materials from other authors without citing them.
- An aware use of materials from other sources without citing them.
- Lack of referencing when using other sources' materials.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 4th Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 14, 34.

2. Which elements should the researcher consider to decide between qualitative and quantitative research approaches?

The central factor to consider is the nature of the research problem; the qualitative research problem demands a deep understanding of the context, circumstance, environment, and milieu from the participants' perspective. In contrast, a quantitative research problem requires describing current conditions, investigating relationships, or proving a theory.²

The central aspect relies on the methods used for data collection and analysis.

The central element is the researcher's ability to work with one approach instead of another.

Both approaches can be used interchangeably as they can respond efficiently to the research problem.

3. The literature review is preceded by systematically gathering relevant and reliable sources for the research problem. What is the utility of the literature review?

It provides the reader, on the one hand, with definitions of variables and treatments examined in the research and justifies the questions; on the other hand, it provides a clear and balanced picture of current leading concepts, theories, and data relevant to the topic of study. It also supports the researcher's claims in the discussion.³

² Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th Edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 135.

³ Bloomberg and Volpe, 352; James P. Sampson Jr., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 38.

- Serves to interpret the main findings of the study.
 - Summarizes the published works on the topic.
 - Backs up the findings of the research.
4. When reading, the researcher must *engage* their source actively and productively as this allows a deep understanding of the extent to which the sources can help to respond to the question. For that, critical reading helps, and it consists of . . .
- Creatively agreeing with a source by adding new insights to the claim or creatively disagreeing as it enables the researcher to lead the topic to better horizons; the researcher reads deliberately to find a problem or look for claims that seem puzzling, inaccurate, or simplistic.**⁴
 - Disapproving source information about the topic.
 - Only identifying the main gaps of the source.
 - Skimming the source’s table of contents, abstract, or introduction.
5. What aspects researcher should consider when paraphrasing, summarizing, or quoting materials?
- Avoid misrepresenting the original author—include arguments that support those materials and the context in which they were extracted, preserving the original author’s claim and reasoning.**⁵

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C Booth et al., 9th ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 45–47.

⁵ Turabian, 52–53.

- Make sure that the most critical parts of the source are included.
 - Using single or double quotation marks depending on the English language type (USA or UK).
 - Only extract the parts that will fit in the text without breaking the flow of the text.
6. An argument persuades readers to agree with the researcher's ideas. What are the argument's main components?
- A *claim* that needs to be backed up, a *reason* to back up the claim and persuade the readers, and the *evidence* that is data gathered from reliable sources to support reason.⁶**
 - Peer-reviewed sources, statistics, and findings interpretations.
 - The main component is a warrant because it links the claim to the reason.
 - Interpretations, warrant, and findings.
7. Readers may question the researcher's answers to the research question. Which of the following sentences elaborates better?
- Readers challenge the intrinsic and extrinsic soundness of the argument. Intrinsically, readers look for problems related to the arguments' evidence, such as their nature, quality, and quantity. Extrinsically, the readers view the argument from other perspectives—noting alternatives or exceptions.⁷**
 - The researcher's poor background in conducting research.

⁶ Turabian, 59.

⁷ Turabian, 41–62.

- The researcher did not back up their claim with sources published in recent years.
 - The researcher did not use warrants in their arguments.
8. What is the difference between the delimitations and limitations of the study?
- Delimitations are anticipated constraints in the interpretation of the findings of the dissertation research, whereas limitations are unanticipated constraints in data interpretation.⁸**
 - The delimitation is related to the study's spatial time and limitation to unanswered questions.
 - The delimitation is related to study participants' inclusion and exclusion criteria, while limitations to the impact of the missing values in the study.
 - Delimitations are related to the study's external validation, while limitations are to internal validation.
9. What is the correct methodology to discuss the study's findings?
- Organized by the research questions or hypotheses, the researcher starts by discussing—in the light of theory, research, education and training, and public policy—those findings that respond to the research questions and have supportive literature. Additional findings whose interpretation can be supported by the presented literature should be enclosed in the discussion**

⁸ James P. Sampson Jr., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd Edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 56, 66.

chapter; the unsupported findings are discussed in the Implication for Future Research section.⁹

- Briefly discuss the less important findings and exhaustively discuss the most important ones.
- Start by discussing the most important findings and end with the least important ones.
- Start by discussing the controversial findings and later with those agreeing with the study's findings.

10. Which of the following best describes the dissertation's conclusions and recommendations chapter?

- Assertions based on and warranted by findings, representing a high level of abstraction, resulting from broad thinking and making new connections among ideas; withdrawn from the study's limitations, consist of clear, doable, and directed to specific groups or people, and include suggestions for further research.¹⁰**
- Summarizes significant findings; identifies what other sources have not answered about the topic.
- Discusses significant findings; shows potential research questions for future research.

⁹ Sampson, 63–66.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 677–81.

- States lessons learned from the literature review and present work; should be doable and actionable;

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.